

Synthesis, Characterisation and Antimicrobial Activities of Binary and Ternary Complexes of UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} Complexes with 5-Hydroxymethyl-8-quinolinol and 8-Formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one with Aniline^ψ

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Synthesis of 5-hydroxymethyl-8-quinolinol and 8-formyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (FHMB) with aniline (FHMBAnil) have been carried out to study the binary and ternary complexes of uranium and thorium. Different analytical techniques have been used to find out the structure of the complexes. They have also been tested for their antimicrobial activities.

A large number of uranium and thorium complexes and their mixed chelates have been reported¹.

We report here the isolation of mixed ligand complexes of UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} containing 2,2'-bipyridylamine with FHMBAnil and binary complexes of UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} with 5-hydroxymethyl-8-quinolinol. The ligands and their metal chelates have been tested for antimicrobial activities.

Binary complex

Ternary complex

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 composition in case of ternary and binary systems respectively. The complexes are neutral because of their non-conducting nature. All complexes possess high melting points. They are coloured, amorphous and stable in air. The complexes are partially soluble in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and insoluble in water and other organic solvents. Hence it was not possible to characterise them by conventional methods like osmometry or viscosity measurements. It was also not possible to measure the molar conductivity due to poor solubility of all metal chelates.

The magnetic moments of the UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} complexes revealed their diamagnetic nature.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit bands corresponding to FHMBAnil, 5-hydroxymethyl-8-quinolinol and 2,2'-bipyridylamine. The broad ir band at $\sim 3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (hydrogen bonded OH) indicates presence of water in the complex. The strong $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band² appears at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The strong medium ligand band at $\sim 1740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is either identical or slightly shifted (by 5–15 cm^{-1}) in the ternary complexes. A sharp medium band at $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed is attributed to aquo-(H–O–H) bending. The use of the absorption due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ in identifying the bonding site is somewhat limited here because of the complex nature of absorption in the region 1500–1630 cm^{-1} . However, the strong ligand band at $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ registers substantial decrease in the intensity after complex formation. The band may be assigned to complex vibration involving C=N, NH_2 and benzene ring³. The various vibrations due to C–C, C–N and C–O for the Schiff base in the two complexes appear at 1090–1280 cm^{-1} . The band at 3090–3050 cm^{-1} (NH) of the free ligand, disappears on complexation indicating the participation of NH group in chelation. The M–N stretching frequency in 2,2'-bipyridylamine complex is obtained at higher wavenumber because of the double bond character of the M–N bond due to $\text{M} \rightarrow \text{N} \pi$ -interaction⁴. The bands around 760 and 650 cm^{-1} may correspond to the coupled M–N vibrations⁵.

Thermal analysis : Thermogravimetric analysis data of the ligand and its metal chelates reveal the following. The ligand 2,2'-bipyridylamine starts decomposing from 110 to 125° and its complete decomposition takes place around 200–225°. Decomposition of the ligand and their metal chelates observed in the TG traces is a single step process. All the complexes show loss in weight corresponding to

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one water molecule in the range 85–100°, indicating the presence of water of crystallisation. The rate of decomposition of the metal chelates is lower than that of the ligand 2,2'-bipyridylamine, suggesting that there may be weak intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Decomposition of all complexes starts above 300°.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE CHELATES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	M	C	H	N
[UO ₂ (5-OH-M-8-quinolinol) ₂].H ₂ O (Brown)	37.20 (37.39)	38.00 37.74	3.00 2.86	4.12 4.40
[Th(5-OH-M-8-quinolinol) ₂].H ₂ O (Light yellow)	38.47 (38.77)	39.89 40.13	2.81 3.00	4.32 4.68
[UO ₂ (2,2'-bipy.A) FHMBAnil].H ₂ O (Orange)	32.20 (32.23)	43.80 43.90	3.12 3.28	8.00 7.59
[Th(2,2'-bipy.A) FHMBAnil].H ₂ O (Yellow)	32.60 (32.86)	46.13 45.89	3.12 3.39	7.48 7.93

Antimicrobial activity : The ligands and their metal chelates were tested against *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (bacteria) and *Aspergillus niger* (fungi). The metal ions were separately tested at equivalent concentration present in 500 ppm metal chelate. The metal ions UO₂^{II} and Th^{IV} showed significant inhibition of all the test organisms, indicating their toxic nature.

The ligand 2,2'-bipyridylamine showed very high inhibitory activity with 10–20% of growth compared to the control. The metal chelates of UO₂^{II} and Th^{IV} showed 60–90% growth of *P. fluorescens* and 5–20% growth of *A. niger*. Thus free metal and ligand showed toxicity towards the growth of microbes but when complexed with ligand it leads to reduction in inhibitory power.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. 2,2'-Bipyridylamine (Fluka) and uranyl and thorium nitrates (B.D.H.) were used. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

Elemental analysis were performed with a Coleman C, H, N analyser. The metal content was determined by standard procedure⁶. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by the Gouy method at room temperature using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and reflectance spectra on a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer using MgO as reference. Thermal measurements were performed using a Du-Pont analyser at a 10° min⁻¹ heating rate in air. Conductance (in ethanol) was measured in a Toshniwal conductivity bridge.

FHMBAnil : 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2.5 g) dissolved in acetic acid (30 ml) was added to hexamethylenetetramine (5.0 g) and the mixture was heated for 6 h on a steam-bath. Then a hot mixture of H₂O

(2.5 ml) and concentrated HCl (15 ml) was added to it and further heated for 10 min. The solution was cooled and the resulting solid extracted with ether to yield FHMB (0.6 g, 60%), m.p. 176°. The Schiff base (FHMBAnil) was prepared by refluxing (1 h) equimolar quantities of FHMB and aniline (freshly distilled) in methanol. The yellow solid that separated on cooling in ice, was washed with 50% methanol and crystallised from methanol, m.p. 160°.

5-Hydroxymethyl-8-quinolinol : A mixture of 8-hydroxyquinoline (7.3 g, 0.05 mol), concentrated HCl (8 ml) and 37% formaldehyde (8 ml, 0.05 mol) was treated with HCl gas for 90 min. The resulting yellow solid 5-chloromethyl-8-quinolinol hydrochloride was dried (0.9 g, 11.5%), m.p. 280°. An aqueous solution of 5-chloromethyl-8-quinolinol (10 g, 0.043 mol) was covered with ether. Dilute ammonia was added to it dropwise with shaking until the aqueous layer was basic to litmus. The layer was then evaporated and dried to yield the product (7.9 g, 99.99%), m.p. 133–36°, which was crystallised from alcohol-benzene.

The complexes : The binary complexes were prepared by taking 0.1 M aqueous solution (10 ml) of uranium or thorium nitrate mixed with 0.1 M 5-hydroxymethyl-8-quinolinol (20 ml). In case of the ternary complexes 1 : 1 : 1 ratio of MAL was used. A 0.1 M solution (10 ml) of uranium or thorium nitrate was mixed with a 0.1 M solution (10 ml) of 2,2'-bipyridylamine. The mixture was stirred and 0.1 M solution (10 ml) FHMBAnil was added, its pH was raised to ~6.0 and ~7.0, respectively, using 0.1 M NaOH. The resulting complexes were washed and dried.

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